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Assessment of Information and Communication Technology Competence among English Language Lecturers in Polytechnics and Colleges of Education in Northwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the Information and Communication Technology competencies between English Language lecturers of Colleges of Education and Polytechnics in North-west Nigeria. One of the objectives of the study is to determine the difference in the level of ICT competencies between English lecturers from federal Colleges of Education and polytechnics in North West, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. A population of 432 (284 male, 148 female) English language lecturers from Polytechnics and Colleges of Education during 2024/2025 academic session in the North-West Nigeria. A sample size of 91 (62 male, 29 female) was selected from the tagged population using stratified sampling technique and proportionate sampling procedure. A 4-point rating scale questionnaire tagged: ICT Competencies among English Lecturers (ICTCAEL) with validity and reliability index of 0.91 was used as instrument for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer two research questions while t-test statistics was used to test two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that, for the ICT competencies, there is no significant difference exists between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West zone, Nigeria. Both have substantial knowledge on the use of computers, email, and internet. The study also revealed that there was significant difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in the area of study and the difference is on the favour of male lecturers. The study concluded that majority of English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics have competencies on most of the ICT tools like power point presentation Microsoft word/excel, email, social media, overhead projector, internet. Other skills are language laboratory, sound system and radio/television assisted instructions. It was recommended that lecturers should be encouraged to be computer literate through organizing regular conferences, seminars, and workshops.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Competences, English Language Lecturers, Colleges of Education, Polytechnics

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Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence is the ability to use a variety of computer applications for varied purposes. Consequently, one of the main predictors of integrating ICT in teaching is teachers' computer proficiency (Ahmed , Qasem, & Power, 2020). The level of competency and knowledge of ICT skills among teachers is different in view of digital technology that exists in varied and wide scope (Wong & Khadijah 2018). Some educators are quick to master the knowledge and technology skills that exist while there are also educators who are still trying to master the most basic technology such as email, students file management system, internet and office productivity software (Wong & Khadijah 2018). The ICT competencies are related with teachers' knowledge and technical training that how to use and maintain ICT equipment and software. These competencies involve the skills to operate modern technologies such as computer, internet etc (Husain, 2010). Regrettably, the majority of developing countries have not been able to successfully investigate the potential applications of computers in their educational systems. It is generally agreed that Nigeria, in particular, was one of the countries that was slow to adopt the use of computers for communication and other purposes (Ogunsola & Aboyade, 2005). Therefore, there is an ongoing need to research, develop, and discuss teachers' professional development and use of digital teaching tools (Amhag, Hellstrom, & Stigmar, 2019).

The introduction of ICT into tertiary institutions has significantly altered the way education is delivered; it paves the way for a new pedagogical approach in which students are expected to play a more active role than in the past (i.e. getting more involved in the teaching and learning process, being active participants of knowledge creation rather than passive recipients of knowledge) (Adamu, Baba, Musa, Goni, Mohammed, & Yohanna, 2020). The incorporation of information technology into the classroom is crucial for ensuring the quality of learning. There are significant benefits to incorporating ICT into the teaching and learning process. Initially, students would become familiar with ICT, since all jobs in today's society depend on ICT (Comfort & Onaigho, 2015). ICT helps facilitate his transaction between producers and users by keeping the students updated and enhancing teachers capacity and ability fostering live contact between the teacher and the student through email, chalk session, e-

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learning, web-based learning including internet, intranet, extranet, CD-ROM, TV and audio-videotape. (Anu, Kapil, Sameer, & Seems 2011)

Statement of the Research Problem

Academic and research communities in Nigeria will soon be required to fully adopt ICTs in order to survive in their respective endeavors as a result of the current trend in technological development. Teachers in the developing world must transform their methods of imparting knowledge and encouraging research through the acquisition of ICTs skills, particularly Internet proficiency (Adamu et al., 2020; Adisa et al., 2018; Comfort & Onaigho, 2015). Therefore the main aim of this study is to investigate lecturers' competencies on the use of ICT tools in Tertiary institutions in North-western Nigeria with particular reference to Colleges of Education and Polytechnics.

Despite the significant expansion in the use of ICTs in several fields, including education, the competency of lecturers and the use of ICT tools at tertiary institutions in North-Western Nigeria, particularly Polytechnics and Colleges of Education, remains a serious issue. This is due to the fact that the beginnings of the teaching and learning by competencies method may be traced to the societal developments of recent decades (Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos et al., 2022). Therefore, digital competence has assumed a prominent position in the educational setting, becoming one of the most important skills that lecturers must possess in the modern world (Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021). Consequently, active-duty lecturers should learn relevant skills to meet the newly increased teaching standards and make adjustments to accommodate the new teaching environment (Gilakjani, 2017).

The objective of Nigeria's tertiary institutions is to produce highly skilled workers for the many economic sectors of the country. It is anticipated to contribute to national development by strengthening and diversifying its programs to meet the nation's high manpower needs and by incorporating national regiments into the professional course curriculum. These objectives could be achieved through effective teaching, research and other allied academic activities (Emmanuel et al., 2022). For teachers of tertiary institutions to carry out their jobs efficiently and effectively especially in this age of knowledge-based technology and globalization, the use of information and communication technology (ICT) becomes imperative recognizing the significance of

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ICT in the development of skills, talents, and competencies for effective development, the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2018) stipulates that it should be incorporated at all levels of education in Nigeria (Emmanuel et al., 2022). Lecturers' competencies in the utilization of ICT tools boost their research productivity. It also boosts their significance in the academic sphere through intellectual contributions. Therefore, information and communication technology (ICT) can play an important role in tertiary institutions in North-Western zone Nigeria. Despite geographical constraints, ICT can provide higher education in rural places in an easily accessible and learning environment. It is critical to therefore investigate how ICT may be used in higher education. North-Western Nigerian states with educational disadvantages can benefit from leveraging the global information network to boost their higher education sector and make better use of current ICT resources. Access to worldwide resources (e-journals, databases, etc.) is made possible by information and communication technology, which strengthens higher education as a whole.

However, Apagu & Wakili, (2015) opined that, the majority of research on ICT in education focuses on the availability of ICT facilities and perspectives of ICT use in national institutions. Researchers place less emphasis on competencies and the prudent use of available ICT tools on the ground. Given the country's economic, social, and political situation, as well as the acceptability of western education in general, particularly in the northern part of the country, therefore, it is questionable whether the lecturers have the necessary ICT competencies to utilize ICT. In the absence of these skills, the enormous amount of money spent on the acquisition of ICT equipment would be a monumental waste, and the learning, teaching, and research objectives of these institutions will not be accomplished. In the light of this, the research aimed at investigating the lecturers' competencies and the use of ICT tools in tertiary institutions in North-Western Nigeria, with a focus on Polytechnics and Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess Information and Communication Technology competencies among English Language Lecturers of Colleges of Education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria. Specifically, the study tried to

1. Determine the difference in the level of ICT competencies between English Language Lecturers in federal colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

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2. Find out the difference in the level of ICT competencies between male and female English Language Lecturers in colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research addressed the following questions:

1. What is the difference in the level of ICT competencies between English Language Lecturers in federal colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the difference in the level of ICT competencies between male and female English Language Lecturers in colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were formulated in the study. They included:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the level of ICT competencies between English Language Lecturers from federal colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the level of ICT competencies between male and female English Language Lecturers in colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted with population of 432 (284 male, 148 female) English language lecturers from Federal Polytechnics and Colleges of Education in the North-West Nigeria. A sample size of 91 (62 male, 29 female) was selected using stratified sampling technique and proportionate sampling procedure. A 4-points rating scale questionnaire titled: ICT Competencies among English Lecturers (ICTCAEL) was used as instrument for data collection. Face to face method of instrument distribution with the help of 5 research assistants was used for data collection. The data collected for analysis was in form of nominal scale converted to interval scale where the most desired value attracts 4 points and the least desired attracts 1 point. The total value of a respondent was arrived at by adding the value of a respondent to each questionnaire item. Mean and

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standard deviation were used to answer research questions while t-test statistics was used to test all hypotheses using SPSS at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference of ICT competencies between English Language lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West of Nigeria?

To answer this research question, the data collected from 51 federal colleges of education English lecturers and 40 from federal polytechnics has been used. Therefore, to find out the difference in their ICT competencies mean and standard deviation was calculated and result presented in table 1 below:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation for difference of ICT competencies between federal colleges of education and federal polytechnics English lecturers in North West Nigeria

Institution	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Federal COE	51	46.43	8.32	3
Federal Poly	40	43.43	6.69	

Fieldwork 2024

Table 1 displayed the mean and standard deviation of lecturers from federal colleges of education and federal polytechnics in North West Nigeria. The mean score and standard deviation in respect of lecturers from federal colleges of education are 46.43 and 8.23. For lecturers from federal polytechnics the mean is 43.43 and standard deviation is 6.69. Their mean difference is 3. The lecturers from federal colleges of education recorded higher mean than their counterpart from federal polytechnics. This shows that there is difference of ICT competence between the groups. However, to know whether it is significance, it is only the data was subjected to t-test independent sample analysis.

Research Question 2: What is the difference of ICT competencies between male and female English language lecturers in the North West Nigeria?

To answer this research question, the data collected from 62 male lecturers and 29 female English lecturers was used to find out the difference in their of ICT

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competencies. The mean and standard deviation as well as mean difference was calculated and result presented in 2 below:

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation for difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of educations and polytechnics in North West Nigeria

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Male	62	47.33	7.70	
Female	29	43.88	7.77	3.45

Fieldwork 2024

Table 2 revealed the mean score of 47.33 and standard deviation of 7.70 for male lecturers while for female, the mean value stands at 43.88 with standard deviation of 7.77. The mean difference was 3.45 in favour of male lecturers. This shows that there was difference of the ICT competence between the genders. However, to know whether the difference is significant it is only when the data was subjected to t-test analysis.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the ICT competencies between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West of Nigeria.

To test null hypothesis 1, t-test independent sample was ran to find out mean difference in the ICT competencies between English lecturers from federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria. The result was presented in the Table 3 below:

Table 3: T-test Analysis of difference in the ICT competencies between English Language lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-Value	p-value	Decision
Federal COE	51	46.43	8.324				
Fed. Polytechnics	40	43.43	6.694	89	1.860	0.07	Retained

Fieldwork 2024

Table 3 showed the t-test statistical analysis on the difference of ICT competencies between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in the area of study. The result revealed the mean value of 46.43 with standard deviation of 8.324 for lecturers from colleges of education while lecturers from polytechnics had mean

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value of 43.43 and standard deviation of 6.694 at degree of freedom of 89 with p-value of 0.07. The p-value obtained is greater than the level of significant 0.05 set for the study. Therefore, null hypothesis was retained and this means that there was no significant difference of ICT competencies between English Language lecturers in federal colleges of education and federal polytechnics in North West Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in tertiary institution in North West of Nigeria.

To test null hypothesis 2, t-test for independent sample on difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria was ran and presented in Table 4 below:

Table 4: T-test Analysis of difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-Value	p-value	Decision
Male	62	47.33	7.70420	229	3.04	0.03	Rejected
Female	29	43.88	7.76786				

Fieldwork 2024

Table 4 contained the t-test statistics on independent samples for the difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria. The analysis revealed the mean values of 47.33 and 43.88 for male and female with standard deviation of 7.70420 and 7.76786 at degree of freedom of 229. The t-value was 3.02 and p-value was 0.03. The p-value obtained was less than the less the level of significant 0.05 set for the study. Therefore, going by decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, it was concluded that there exist significant difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West of Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study shows that for the ICT competencies, no significant difference exists between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West,

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Nigeria. Both of them have substantial knowledge on use of computers, email, internet, social network etc. This finding is not in agreement with work of Adeoluwa, & Ogunmodede, (2018) who investigated on the lecturers' competency and utilisation of ICT facilities in the delivery of accounting lecturers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State. Their finding shows that the use of ICT facilities depends on the level of competency of lecturers. This helps them to increase their efficacy in classroom teaching, research and publications. Thus, lecturers who are competent in the use of ICT tools can easily download new materials from the internet which can be used for lecture preparation and teaching.

The study revealed that there is significant difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in the area of study. This finding disagree with Ahmed, et'al (2020) who conducted a study aimed at exploring South Yemeni EFL tertiary teachers' attitude towards implementing ICTs in their English Language teaching. Their findings revealed that English as Foreign Language (EFL) teachers of the concerned universities held positive attitudes towards using ICTs in their teaching of English and there is no significant difference in teachers' attitudes that can be attributed to gender, academic level or computer competence.

Conclusion

It is the conclusion of the study that the majority of English lecturers in federal college of education and polytechnic have competencies on most of the ICT tools like power point presentation Microsoft word/excel, email, social media, overhead projector and internet. Other skills are language laboratory, sound system and radio/television assisted instructions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings it was recommended that;

1. Lecturers should be encouraged to be computer literate through organizing regular conferences, seminars, and workshops. Similarly, they should be encouraged to develop good attitude toward use of ICT tools for teaching and research work.

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2. The managements of colleges of education and polytechnics should make provisions for e-learning facilities as well as capacity building in the use of facilities in their institutions. Hence, special interest should be on female lecturers to enhance their level of competencies.

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